

MODERN MECHANISMS OF STUDENT KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT AND CONTROL IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Most of the population of today's rapidly developing world can speak two or more languages. Of course, the first of these languages is one's own mother tongue, and many linguists believe that special conditions should be created for mastering not only the studied foreign language, but also the mother tongue. It should be noted that the new generation growing up as a result of the reforms in the field of learning foreign languages, from the educational institution to the higher education institution, compares the native language and the foreign language at the same time. they learn This method helps to create a language environment during the lesson.

In recent years, the interest in learning foreign languages has increased significantly. This is also due to the decrees, measures and measures of our country aimed at developing foreign languages after independence. This is why we, foreign language teachers, offer different types of foreign language lessons in order to increase students' interest in foreign languages. innovation requires the use of methods and technical tools. One such method is the use of role-playing games in the course of the lesson. Role-playing games are the application of different situations in our real life in the process of learning a foreign language. This method helps to create a language environment in the course of the lesson. I use a lot of role-playing games in the course of the lesson. For example: You can give students situations such as a conversation about students' future plans. According to these situations, students perform scenes. Such life-like role-playing games create a language environment in the course of the lesson, and give students the opportunity to freely express their thoughts. In the process of participating in role-playing games, students learn to think, learn to express their emotional states freely in a foreign language. In the process of preparing for role-playing games, they correct each other's lexical, grammatical and pronunciation mistakes. Making a mistake and correcting it also helps to learn the language and teaches students the correct pronunciation. In addition, role-playing games increase students' interest in learning a foreign

language and create a lively, cheerful atmosphere for the lesson. This serves to increase the effectiveness of foreign language lessons.

After our country gained independence, interest in teaching foreign languages increased and many opportunities were created for young people. As our first president, Islam Karimov, said, "Currently, the teaching of foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing. There is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place in the world community today, and for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening comprehension and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It also envisages increasing the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening comprehension and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the student is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process, including:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons;
- it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs;
- CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of foreign language learning more interesting and effective for students.

Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in higher education. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which ensures that students demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Training for educational games subjects should be taken as a basis. During the games, the student is more interested in this exercise than in a regular lesson and works freely. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching.

Students participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher provides education to the student through them. A student believes that he can speak, listen,

understand, and write in English while playing games, he is interested. We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently.

Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues from the United States of America and England:

- To apply this method of "Creative Problem Solving", the beginning of the story is read, and the students' judgment is referred to how it ends;
- "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to a riddle by thinking;
- "Quick answers" help to improve the efficiency of the lesson; - "Chigil yazdi" ("Warm-up exercises") using various games in the classroom to interest students in the lesson;
- "Pantomime" (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are done and students are tired;

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English lessons, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for classes. This turns students into active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will be able to effectively use innovative technologies. We can contribute as we develop them further.

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